

“A Study To Assess The Self Harming Behaviour Among Adolescents In A Selected School , Thrissur”

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Abstract: Self-harm is a behavior that emerges among children and Adolescent in which a child or Adolescent commits an act with a purpose of physically or psychologically harming himself or herself with or without a real intent of suicide. Self harm is not a solution; it's just an escape from the problem. Self harm refers to the act of intentionally hurting one self. Some of the causes for the self-harming behavior are peer influence, poor academic performance media influence and inability to cope up with the stress in life. Hence the study Was undertaken to assess the self harming behavior among Adolescent in selected school, Thrissur. The other objectives of the study were to assess the self harming behavior among Adolescent and to associate the self-harming behavior among adolescence with their selected demographic variables. Data was collected by using structured checklist .The design of the study was descriptive survey and was conducted on 120 students from St. Vincent pallotti central school, Kallathode, Thrissur. The samples Were selected by non-random sampling. The result shows that out of 120 samples 8.32% have severe self-harmingbehavior,54.18%havemoderateself harming behavior and 37.5% have mild self-harming behavior. There was association between the self-harming behavior and selected demographic variable According to this study, there was moderate self-harming behavior among Adolescent.

Key Words: *Self Harming Behaviour,Adolescents*

INTRODUCTION: Self-harm is a behaviour that emerges among children and Adolescent in which a child or Adolescent commits an act with a purpose of physically or psychologically harming himself or herself with or without a real intent of suicide. The behaviour involves the deliberate craving , cutting, scratching or burning of the skin with fingernails or other objects sharp enough to cause injury. Navigating through a dynamic world punctuated with challenges and impediments is sure to brings anxieties and insecurities in people. Inability to cope with theses can resort one to self harm, where individuals intentionally harm themselves, either physically or psychologically, often without any real intent of ending their lives. Though Adolescent are the highly susceptible demography, this issue is not confined to any specific social or economic group; rather, it permeates our society at large. Unfortunately, in India, the plight of these young individuals who engage in self-infliction or associated risky behaviours

has often been overlooked, not only by families but also by the broader community and the government. It is high time we address this growing concern. In this juncture Marcus Aurelius wise saying you have the power over your mind, not outside event' bear testament to the profound connection between one's internal world and their strength

NEED AND SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

Self-harm an act with nonfatal outcome in which an individual deliberately initiates a non habitual behaviour, that without intervention from others will cause self-harm or deliberately ingest a substance in excess of the prescribed or generally recognized therapeutic dosage and which is aimed at realising changes that the person desires via the actual or expected physical consequences

A study to assess the self harming behavior among Adolescent in selected school Thrissur.

Objective

- To assess the self harming behavior among Adolescent
- To associate the self harming behavior among Adolescent with their selected demographic variables

HYPOTHESIS

Significant at 0.05 level

H_1 : There is a significant association between the selected demographic variables and self harming behaviour among Adolescent.

RESEARCH APPROACH

RESEARCH APPROACH: In this study quantitative research was used

METHODS OF DATA COLLECTION

Data collection procedure is the means of gathering information to address the research problem. data collection was done on 16/08/2023 A formal permission was obtained from the principal Aswini college of nursing thrissur .The study was conducted in St.Vincent Pallotti central school, Thrissur. Firstly the investigator established a good rapport with the students and started to gather data from the students. Oral consent was obtained from students. a total number of 120 samples was selected through purposive sampling technique. a demographic data was collected initially, and the structured questionnaire was given to the sample .The samples were advised to answer the question and return the tool after 15 minutes. the samples were cooperative during the time of data collection

RESEARCH DESIGN

For the present study, descriptive survey design was adopted.

DEMOGRAPHIC VARIABLES

In the study the demographic variables are age, gender, class of study, birth order, number of siblings, type of family, occupation of father, occupation of mother, family residence and hobbies

POPULATION

Adolescent girls and boys in the age group 15-18 studying in St. Vincent Pallotti central school, Kalathode, Thrissur

TARGET POPULATION

The total number of people or objects that meet the designated set of criteria. For the present study, the target population includes students from all over Thrissur.

ACCESSIBLE POPULATION

It is the aggregate of cases that confirm to designated the criteria and are accessible as subjects of the study. The present study, accessible population belongs to 11th and 12th std of St. Vincent Pallotti central school, Kalathode, Thrissur

SAMPLING TECHNIQUE

The samples were collected through purposive sampling technique

SAMPLING SIZE

The sample of the present study consists of 120 students in St. Vincent Pallotti central school, Kalathode, Thrissur

SAMPLING CRITERIA

Inclusion criteria : The criteria that specify the characteristics the subject in the population must possess are referred to as eligibility criteria or inclusion criteria"

- Students who are from the age group of 15 to 18 years
- The sample who are willing to participate in the study.

Exclusion criteria : For this study exclusion criteria were:

- Adolescent students who were absent on day of data collection.
- Adolescent students who were not willing to participate in the study.

Section-A demographic profile of Adolescent

The demographic profile consists of variables such as age, sex, type of family, family income, birth order, educational status of father and mother, family residence, place of the residence of the student, number of the siblings, class of study, frequency of anger related episodes, behavioral effects of the anger, the triggers etc.

Section-B: structured knowledge questionnaire to assess self harming behaviour among Adolescent

Knowledge checklist regarding the self-harming behaviour which consist of 15 questions, The right

answer carries one mark and the wrong answer carries No mark.

RESULT FINDINGS

Section A

Description of socio demographic variables of adolescent students

Table 1: Frequency and percentage distribution of social demographic variables of adolescence with respect to their age in years ,Gender and class of study

SI.NO	DEMOGRAPHIC VARIABLES	FREQUENCY	
			PERCENTAGE
1.	Age in years		
	a) 15	6	5%
	b) 16	60	50%
	c) 17	51	42.5%
	d) 18	3	2.5%
2.	Gender		
	a) male	59	49.16%
	b) female	61	50.84%
3.	Class of study		
	a) plus one	54	45%
	b) plus Two	66	55%

Table 2: Frequency and percentage distribution of social demographic variables of Adolescence with respect to their birth order, number of siblings, Type of family

SI.NO	DEMOGRAPHIC VARIABLES	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
1.	Birth order		
	a)1	65	54.1
	b)2	47	39.16
	c)3	8	6.67
	d)4	0	0
2	Number of siblings		

	a)1	85	70.84
	b)2	22	18.33
	c)3	9	7.5
	d)4	4	3.33
3	Type of family		
	a)Nuclear	89	74.16
	b)Joint	30	25
	c)Extended	1	0.84

Table 3: Frequency and percentage distribution of social demographic variables of

Adolescence with respect to the occupation of father, occupation of mother, family residence.

SL NO	DEMOGRAPHIC VARIABLES	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE %
1	Occupation of father		
	a)Government	20	16.66
	b)Business	49	40.84
	c)Daily wages	6	5
	d)other	45	37.5
2	Occupation of mother		
	a)Government	30	25
	b)business	3	10.84
	c)daily wage	2	10
	d)homemaker	65	54.16
3	Family residence		
	a)urban	88	73.3
	b)rural	32	26.7
4	Hobbies		
	a)watching movies	27	25
	b)listing to music	51	10.84

c)playing games	16	10
d)others	26	54.16

SECTION B

Distribution of samples according to level of knowledge.

Interpreting the level of knowledge among the total samples.

Table 2: Level of knowledge among Adolescent in selected school

SI.NO	Level of knowledge	Frequency	Percentage
1.	Severe self harm behavior	10	8.32%
2.	Moderate self harm behavior	65	54.18%
3.	Mild self harm behavior	45	37.5%

DISCUSSION

The present study aimed to assess the knowledge of self harming behaviour among adolescents in a selected school, Thrissur .

In the present study shows that out of 120 adolescents, 45 sample are mild knowledge on self harming(37.5%), 65 people (54.18%) had moderate knowledge on self harming , and 10 people (8.32%)had severe knowledge on self harming behaviour.

The second objective was to find out the association between the self harming behaviour with selected demographic variables In the present study shows that there is no significant knowledge of self harming among the adolescents with the selected demographic variable such as age in years ($\chi^2= 7.859$)12.59 level, Class of study ($\chi^2= 4.8991$) 5.99level, no significance on birth order ($\chi^2= 4.11$)12.59 level, no significance on number of siblings ($\chi^2= 10.5342$)12.59 level,

type of family ($\chi^2= 4.168$)9.49 level, occupation of father ($\chi^2= 4.0886$)12.59 level, occupation of mother ($\chi^2=8.5619$)12.59 level, family residence ($\chi^2=0.2561$)5.99 level.

CONCLUSION

Self harm among young people is common and is significant public health issue due to the immediate and potential longer term physical harm it causes, as well as its association with psychological distress while self harm can be a short lived reaction to a period of distress without long term implications and also indicate deployment of mental health problems, including attempted and completed suicide in later life.

According to the study ,the knowledge regarding self harming behaviour among adolescents is adequate. The result of this study points out that each school should give some attention

to the knowledge of self harming among adolescents because these adolescents are future hope's of the nation.

Training on general behavior should be given to the adolescents and here the educational institution also plays a major role side by side the family. Based on this study we suggest that the institutions or school should include some extracurricular activities which is related to the improvement behavioural pattern of the individual and which involves productive personalities out of the adolescents.

So, we conclude that self harming behaviour does not solve anything. It builds nothing, but destroys everything. So adolescents should learn to control self harming behaviour and that makes them deviate from the path of life that should have chosen.

1. Michelle Miller, Marcus Redley, Et al, "Understanding reasons for self harm in adolescent girls", International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health, April 2021. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC8037877/>
2. Ambrose J.Melson, Rory C. O'Connor, "Differentiating adults who think about self harm from those who engage in self harm", October 2019. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC8037877/>
3. Rory C O'Connor, Susan Rasmussen, Et al, "Distinguishing Adolescent who think about self harm from those who engage in self harm", British journal of psychiatry, April 2012. Available from: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/22403089/>
4. Janis Whitlock, "self injurious behaviour in Adolescent May 2010. Available from: <https://journals.plos.org/plosmedicine/article?id=10.1371/journal.med.1000240>
5. Emmanuel Nii-BoyeQuarshie, FaragShuwiehdi, Et al, "Self harm among in-school and street-connected Adolescent in Ghana", Public health research, Available from <https://bmjopen.bmj.com/content/11/1/e041609>
6. Louziela p. Masana, Marc Eric s. Reyes, Et al, "uncovering the mystery of non suicidal self injury among selected Filipino Adolescent in 2021" Psychological Studies, August 6 2021. Available from <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s12646-021-00619-6#~:text=A%20few%20studies%20elucidated%20NSSI%20cases%20in%20the%20Philippines>
7. JenniferJMuehlenkap, Laurance Claus, Et al," International prevalence of Adolescent non suicidal self injury and deliberate self harm" Child and Adolescent Psychiatry and Mental health, March 30 2012. Available from <https://capmh.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/1753-2000-6-10>
8. Paul Moran et al," the natural history of self- harm from adolescence to young adulthood", National library of medicine,2012. Available from: [https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/22100201/#text=We%20recorded%20a%20substantial%20reduction,boys%20\(1%2F764](https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/22100201/#text=We%20recorded%20a%20substantial%20reduction,boys%20(1%2F764)
9. Becky Mars, Jon Heron,Et al, predictors of future suicide attempt among Adolescent with suicidal thoughts or non- suicidal self-harm ', National library of medicine, April 2019. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC6494973/>
10. Keith Hawton , Karen Rodham , Et al , "Deliberate self harm in Adolescent", British Journal Of Psychiatry, November 2002 . Available from : <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/12446536/>
11. Yvette Morey , Dominic Mellon ,Et al

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